

The Effectiveness of Social Media as a Marketing and Promotion Tool to Increase Consumer Purchase Intention in the Food and Beverage Industry Burger Garage Jakarta

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ABSTRACT: This study develops a new social media strategy for Burger Garage.

Three years have passed since the COVID-19 Pandemic, and the market for Food and Beverage has been changing. This study will help Burger Garage develop its Social Media Strategy to reach its yearly target. Burger Garage has been active in its social media but has yet to reach its full potential. This is due to an underdeveloped marketing channel that needs a clear plan to succeed.

This study analyzes their social Media using external and internal studies. External analysis uses 5 Porter analysis and competitor analysis, while internal analysis will explore using the capabilities of the study. The research also used questionnaires to understand the customers; it targeted Burger Garage customers and gathered 200 respondents to give their thoughts on their marketing strategy, social media promos, and their activities in social media. This research included in-depth interviews and observation with Burger Garage owner. To conclude, this paper analyzes Burger Garage's business approach and suggests improving its marketing and social media to succeed in the Food and Beverage market.

KEYWORDS: Food, Promotion, Social Media.

1. INTRODUCTION

1. Importance of the topic

The first chapter will discuss a brief background of the research, focusing on the impact of social media on food and beverage companies from Indonesia and how food and beverage companies affect Indonesia economically. The background will follow the environment, the study's aim, the research question's scope, and the research scope and limitations.

1.1. Backgrounds

Social Media in today's society refers to a computer-based technology that facilitates the sharing of ideas, thoughts, and information based virtual networks, and communities. A famous quote from Ardath Arbee, CEO of Marketinginteraction.com stated that "*Social Media can provide a conversational extension to a B2B company's nurturing programs. Social Media allows us to humanize our communications and make our companies more approachable*". The quotes describe the uniqueness of using social media as a marketing tool, this helps the company be more approachable for customers that want to engage with companies such as buying the product, promoting the usage of the product, and many more. Social media as a tool for communication with customers has been changed greatly over the years therefore businesses must learn how to use social media in a way that is consistent with their business plan, especially for companies starving to gain an advantage by using social media Paquette, H (2013).

Figure 1.1 Percentage Essential Digital Headline Indonesia.

Source: AJ Marketing.

Indonesia has the fourth largest population in the world, with 276.4 million, with 212 million internet users, making social media marketing one of the dominating forms of marketing and advertising in this country (AJMarketing,2023). With the pandemic ongoing, marketing experts have had to get even more creative and strategic with their campaigns. Social media Indonesia has active users of 167 million or 60.4% of Indonesian people use social media. The percentage scale is large, showing that Indonesian people are active users.

This research will focus on food and beverage companies that develop and use social media to expand their marketing strategy. This phenomenon has only developed within the last decade, and this is why social media has primarily focused on (1) defining the explanation of new technology and concepts that make up its foundation and (2) exploring the impact of company integration of social media consumer behavior Paquette, H (2013). In addition, this research will discuss the marketing tools using social media and how social media can affect F & B companies as promotion tools.

1.1.1 Social Media

Figure 1.2 Chart of Most used Social Media Platform In Indonesia

Source: INSG.GO

Indonesia, with 276.4 Million people, the fourth largest in the world, has activities on the internet, most notably using social media. The graph shows that Indonesians use Whatsapp the most because people love to chat, connect with friends or family, and for business purposes.

Social media marketing uses platforms to connect with the audience to build a brand, increase sales, and drive website traffic. It will involve sharing great content on social media profiles, listening to music and engaging with followers, analyzing the results, and running social media advertisements. There are several social media platforms: Facebook, Instagram, TikTok, Twitter, Pinterest, Youtube, and Snapchat.

In 2020, it was a challenging year for businesses in every sector because of the Covid-19 Pandemic, and it will affect the Food and Beverage business. Several businesses were closed because of the pandemic, and several businesses felt the effect of decreasing sales in the first few months when the pandemic started. In Indonesia, dining trends in the Food and Beverage industry have been redefining; spending more time at home during the pandemic meant ordering more food deliveries. According to VERTEX, S (2022), Indonesian food deliveries service saw strong growth in 2021, with 24.3% of growth in merchandise value (GMV), increasing to USD\$ 4.6 billion from USD\$ 3.7 billion in 2020 (VERTEX, S, 2022).

Therefore in the Pandemic era it concluded that all of Food and Beverage businesses are heading to online platforms, this effect social media becoming more affecting as their primary promotion tools for the business to stay relevant.

1.1.2. Food and Beverage in Indonesia

Figure 1.3 Chart Food and Drink Service Industry

Source: Spire

In Indonesia, as seen in the graph, culinary has contributed to Indonesia's Economy since the Pandemic started. Culinary has the highest percentage at 41%, followed by Fashion at 18%, Handmade craft at 15%, and TV Radio at 8%, as they have contributed to the Indonesia Economy since 2020. This is because in Indonesia, people focus on the culinary business as their primary creative alternative to maintaining Economic income.

Figure 1.4 Chart Food Ingredients or Product Sourcing from Indonesia F&B Industry.

Source: Spire

Based on Bahar, J (2020), in the past five years, food product sourcing has been increasing in the industry by 8.86%. This is because the culinary business in Indonesia is growing because MSME players have come to this business. Moreover, in Indonesia, there has been a trend that Indonesians eat out at least once a day. This causes their global average to increase to 9%. Therefore, this will make Indonesian people become more conscience of food quality, and this will make them purchase more food, resulting in demand for food and delivery options in Indonesia (Food and Service in Indonesia, 2018). After examining the culinary sectors, the report will focus on Jakarta Area culinary because most food and beverage business comes from the capital city in Indonesia.

1.1.3. Food and Beverage in Jakarta

In Jakarta, the food and beverage industry is an important sector supporting the performance of the non-oil and gas processing industry. In the first quarter of 2022, the Food and beverage industry has the third contributed in GDP of 37.77%

When the pandemic started in 2020, the food and beverage industry had been hit hard as people opted to stay rather than go to the restaurant; therefore, the industry hit hard for business (Jakarta Post,2020). Based on the data from PT. Moka Teknologi Indonesia, the most homegrown startup that uses digital cashier service, has experienced losses due to the pandemic, including the F&B sector. In Indonesia, 13 out of 17 cities have experienced a significant decrease in their daily earning Jakarta Post,(2020)

1.2. Business Issue

Figure 1.8 Burger Garage Omzet

Burger Garage has been established since 2021. From there the company Omzet has been upward from sales but never reached their goals of 200 million per year. In 2021 the first month was stable in the 50 million range but after the pandemic started and the country was locked down every business closed for a month, until the owner started opening again and focusing on Online Delivery. In 2022 it started well for Burger Garage reaching 100 million in the first month. This outcome in 2022 is increasing every month because every business is starting back after the pandemic but still has several regulations to obey such as social distancing, minimum person eating in the restaurant, and limited operations. Burger Garage will have its success in 2022 but the sales have not achieved their target of 200 million per month, and it shows a lack of social media marketing as their promotion tools still need to be improved in order to achieve the target.

In the F&B industry, of course, it has a relationship with the perspective of technological developments and especially social media, which in fact is one of the best marketing media, on the social media side which includes Instagram. Burger Garage is relatively less able to utilize and interact with its followers, as evidenced by engagement data. The rate is 2.47 percent which states that Burger Garage's engagement rate is still smaller than the average engagement rate on Instagram, which is ideally worth 4.80 percent for followers in the range of five thousand to twenty thousand.

The graph shows that in 2021 Southeast Asia estimated the value of food delivery transactions to be around IDR 78.4 Trillion (Kurre, E, 2022). Most food delivery comes from three platforms: Gofood, Grab, and Shopee Food, Indonesia's leading online food delivery. However, when the pandemic started in 2020, the food industries were threatened by social distancing and the government not allowing restaurants to dine in.

In today's age, Online Food Deliver has become part of people's daily lives because most consumers use Online Food Delivery to support productivity, explore the latest culinary trends, and socialize (Kurre, E, 2022). Based on the research from Southeast Strategic Economic Research Lead Stella Kusumawardhani, more than half of consumers receive Online Food Delivery at least once a week. Moreover, this service is used by almost all levels of society with fixed income, and a majority of users is Generation Z of 43% and millennials 39% (Kurre,E,2022).

Social media plays a significant role in marketing and promotion tools as well as having a relationship with customers. In the era of high-quality technology, small businesses are beginning to use social media as a marketing tool (Cox, Sarah., 2012). According to a report from We Are Social Media, the number of social media users worldwide in 2019 is estimate at 3.484 billion (Chaffey, Dave., 2019). In 2019, every company needs to have a social media platform. As a business owner or marketer having social media is a benefit for your company, this helps the company brand recognition and sales of your product and increases company profits. Every owner must follow the top new channels, trends, and current activity in their markets so that they can keep up in today's market (Mcleod, Betsy., 2018).

In this digital era, social media attract young entrepreneurs who want to use their platform to market their products, including those from the culinary world. Chefs, food business owners, and restaurants are focusing on improving their digital marketing skills to gain new customers that are always receiving further information about Culinary advertisements in via social media (The Jakarta post-life team, 2016). According to social bakers (2018), Facebook is the top social media platform for people in Indonesia, with four million users in 2018. Facebook has the highest interaction rate with 400 thousand of users, so this means Facebook users will give businesses feedback for their products. This helps them improve their products. For Facebook, the top industry user is fast-moving consumer goods focusing on food and beverage with an estimated 82 thousand users (Social Bakers, 2018).

In relation to this research, the issue that will be tackled is how social media can improve Food and Beverage companies in Indonesia. Most Food and Beverage companies have been struggling from the pandemic in 2020. Therefore most of the business has been struck badly and shut down because the income is decreasing. Social Media have been the tools for Food and Beverage companies to survive, but there are several companies that need guidance to use social media. Therefore, this research will help companies to use social media properly and can gain more exposure.

1.4. Research Question

- Q1. How does the influence of social media promotion on consumer buying interest in burger garage?
- Q2. What is the influence of social media influencers on consumer buying interest at burger garage?
- Q3. How does the influence of social media promotions on consumer buying interest in burger garages with brand trust as the moderator variable?
- Q.4 How does the influence of social media influencers on consumer buying interest in burger garages with brand trust as the moderator variable?
- Q5. How effective can social media be used to promote Burger Garage to food and beverage customers?

1.5. Aims of the study

This study aims to determine how effective social media is for food and beverage such as Burger Garage Jakarta. In addition to knowing the effect, this research also aims to determine whether social media influences consumers in buying decisions for Burger Garage, so it will show how the companies grow in the Indonesian market.

1.6. Research scope and Limitation

The final project will focus on analyzing the performance of F&B company Burger Garage in social media activity. The company has been in business for three years. However, when the Pandemic started, the industry started slow because of the Pandemic;

therefore, this research will dive deeply into the usage of social media and the effectiveness of using social media in the Jakarta F&B market.

2. LITERATURE REVIEW

2.1. Problem Exploration

To support the research, the author will discuss the problem and theories that will support the research and use references according to the variables studied for this research. At the end of the chapter, the framework and the problem will continue from the last chapter.

2.1.1. Business Situation Analysis

In this business situation the report will discuss the effect of social media as a promotion tools for burger garage. Based on the interview from the owner of Burger Garage, the business goals is to have 200 Million per month as their primary target to achieve good conditional sales. Right now Burger Garage is in good condition after a pandemic two years ago. In Covid 19 pandemic most of the businesses are closed especially for Burger Garage, but time passes and the pandemic is over. The business starts again and returns to normal. Although everything back to normal Burger Garage still has not achieved the sales that were projected from the owner, the business needs to achieve 200 million Rupiah per month to achieve success. Therefore Burger Garage wants to optimize their strategy by using social media to attract new customers, this will help them to have recognition in their area and many new customers will order via online or eating in the restaurants.

2.1.2. Stakeholder Analysis

Table 2.1 Stakeholder Analysis

Table with 3 columns: StakeHolder, Main Interest, Power and Influence. Rows include Owner, Customer, Employee, and Influencer with their respective interests and powers.

The table above will discuss the stakeholders being analyzed in the report. This report consists of four stakeholders that will analyze: Owner, Customers, Employee, and Influencer. Every stakeholder will have the influence that will affect by using social media as a promotion tool, such as

- Owner: the main goals for an owner are achieving profit for the business and sustainability growth for the business to succeed in the future.
Customer: the main goals for customers are having a good experience, good quality, and eating good food from burger garage.
Employee: In stakeholder, the benefit for workers are searching for a new opportunity, new skills, and new experience to improve in their area.
Influencer: Influence benefits it for exposure for them and the business with high number of followers. The influencer can attract many new customers for the business.

The analysis will be based on the question that been given by researcher to order to have indept analysis to the stake holder. There four type of question each of them are for the stakeholder:

Question owner:

1. What is your main reason to create/ to eat/ to work at burger garage?
2. What are the businesses using for marketing campaigns?
3. How much Omzet for a month?

Question employee:

1. How long have you been working in Burger Garage?
2. Why are you working in a restaurant business?
3. Are there any skills that have been taught while working here?

Question for Customer:

1. Why are you eating at Burger Garage?
2. How do you know Burger Garage?
3. How is the food or service Burger Garage?

Question for influencer:

1. How do you Endorse Burger Garage?
2. How many followers do you have?
3. Why is the reason to endorse burger garage?

2.2. Theoretical Foundation

To support The research, the author describes some theories that support the research and uses references according to variables studied for this research. At the end of this chapter, the framework and analysis hypotheses, a follow-up discussion of the previous chapter, are described.

2.2.1. Marketing Strategy

This section will discuss marketing strategy and the tools that will be used for this research. Marketing strategy is based on a business's overall game plan for targeting prospective consumers and turning them into customers for the company (Barone, A, 2023). Marketing strategy contains the company value proposition, key brand messaging, target customers or demographics, and high-level elements to ensure the company clearly understands its targets (Barone, A,2023). The marketing strategy goals are to achieve and communicate with their customers and maintain rival companies to understand the needs and wants of their customers. Several promotions have been used, such as mass customization and social media campaigns. This asset is based on effectively communicating a company's core value proposition.

Creating a marketing strategy requires a few steps such as:

1. Identify your goals: having goals can help identify short-term goals such as establishing authority, increasing customer engagement, or generating leads. This also can measure benchmarks for progressing your marketing plan.
2. Know your clients: Every service must have ideal customers to manage their product to meet the exact requirement of the clients. This also needs to establish who your client is and how your product will improve their situation.
3. Create your message: After identifying the goals, it is time to create their message. This is an opportunity for companies to show their potential clients their product service and its benefit.
4. Define budget: before identifying the messaging process, it is better to define the budget that is going to be used by the company for advertising the product. With secure funding, the company can be a viral moment on social media organically.
5. Determine your channels: Companies must find good value in creating social media posts. This can be an opportunity for the advertising to become a success; therefore, companies need to find an appropriate venue for your content.
6. Measure your success: To target the company's marketing, they need to know whether it can reach the audience. Therefore determine the metrics and how can judge the success of marketing efforts.

2.3 Conceptual Framework and Hypothesis Research

In this part of the section, it will discuss the conceptual framework that models the theory that will be used and the goals for identifying the issue, and it will discuss the Hypothesis Research section for answering the research problem using methods for finding the solution of the problems.

2.3.1 Conceptual Framework

The framework is a conceptual model of how the theory relates to various factors identified as important issues. A good framework will explain theoretically the link between the variables studied. So theoretically, it is necessary to explain the relationship between

the independent and dependent variables (Sugiyono, 2017). Below will be presented the relationship between the variables in the study, namely as follows:

Figure 2.1 Framework Design

2.3.2 Hypothesis Research

The hypothesis is a temporary answer to the formulation of the research problem. It is said to be temporary, because the answers given are only based on relevant theories, not based on empirical facts obtained through data collection (Sugiyono, 2017). Based on the description of the framework above, the hypotheses formed are as follows:

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H1: Social Media Promotion has an effect on consumer buying interest.

H2: Social media influencer has an effect on consumer buying interest

H3: Social Media Promotion has an effect on consumer buying interest with brand trust as a moderation variable.

H4: Social media influencer has an effect on consumer buying interest with brand trust as a moderation variable.

3. RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

3.1 Data Collection

Sugiyono (2015) stated that, "Data collection techniques can be done by interview, questionnaire, observation and a combination of the three."

In this study, the primary data used was through a questionnaire, the object of the questionnaire was the Consumer of the Burger Garage. The questionnaires that have been provided online are distributed through social media so that respondents simply click on the existing link and then can immediately fill out the questionnaire. The advantage of this online questionnaire is that it is able to streamline time in data collection and is more effectively used so that data collection can be obtained immediately. Meanwhile, secondary data through this method is obtained through interviews, scientific journals, study results from previous researchers, lecture notes, and other relevant sources.

3.1.1 Data Source

According to Sugiyono (2016) states that:

1. Primary sources are data sources that directly provide data to data collectors. In this study, primary data were obtained from the results of questionnaires, observations, and interviews with respondents or related parties
2. Secondary sources are data sources that do not directly provide data to data collectors, for example through other people or through documents. In this study, secondary data were obtained from relevant supporting literature in supporting this research.

3.1.2 Population

Talking about the population, Sugiyono (2019) suggests that the population is the scope of research that includes objects that have characteristics. so that it can be determined and studied.

The population for this study is consumers and social media users who follow Burger Garage and have made purchases at Burger Garage.

3.1.2 Sample

The sample is the part and characteristics possessed by the population (Sugiyono, 2012). Based on the population that has been determined, in order to make it easier for researchers to conduct research, a sample is needed that is useful when the population under study is large, where the sample must be representative of the total population. So that sampling from the population is representative of the total population, every subject in the population has an equal chance of being a sample.

There are several requirements in the number of sample calculations according to Solimun (2002) based on the guidelines in determining the sample size as follows:

1. If the parameter estimation uses the maximum likelihood estimation method, the recommended sample size is between 100 to 200 respondents, with a minimum sample of 50.
2. As much as 5 to 10 times the number of parameters available in the model.
3. Equal to 5 to 10 times the number of manifest variables (indicators) of all latent variables.

According to Hair et al., (2017) the sample criteria in the use of PLS-SEM are at least 5 times the number of indicators. Because the number of indicators for this research is 22, the researcher determines a sample of 22 x 5, which is 110 samples.

3.2 Research Methodology

This research adopts a mixed methods approach. The mixed methods research design is a process of collecting, analyzing, and combining quantitative and qualitative research findings in a comprehensive study (Creswell & Clark, 2015). The mixed methods

are designed simultaneously with the aim of obtaining data and answering research questions comprehensively. Sugiyono (2014) also asserts that mixed methods research integrates both quantitative and qualitative methods side by side to achieve comprehensive, valid, reliable, and objective data. The use of mixed methods is intended to produce more accurate data when relying on one type of data alone is not sufficient. The combination of both methods provides better understanding and insights.

In this study, the researcher employed a sequential explanatory design. The sequential explanatory design combines quantitative and qualitative methods, starting with a quantitative survey and then followed by exploring qualitative data through interviews, observations, and literature reviews (Sugiyono, 2014). The role of quantitative data in this research is to measure descriptive data. Subsequently, qualitative data serves to deepen, develop, and expand upon the quantitative data obtained earlier.

In quantitative research with the aim of providing an overview of the important relationship of each indicator. The research was carried out quantitatively, namely processing the numbers on the measurement of variables and indicators in research, to then be processed into data and then carried out an analysis so that in the end a conclusion is produced.

3.3 Research Design

Research design framework is research methods and techniques that are chosen by the author to conduct the research that will be implemented. The foundation, step and methodology of this research design helps the author to seek the problem solving of this research. Research design that will be used and will be analyzed is shown in the figure below.

Figure 3.1 Research Design

As seen in Figure above, the author arranges and conceptualizes the conceptual framework for research to be further examined based on the business problems raised in the previous chapter related to the failure to achieve the revenue target from burger garage. With these problems Burger Garage requires corrective steps that need to be taken by the management promotion of Burger Garage, one of the steps that will try to be analyzed and implemented in the future by evaluating and perfecting the previous business and development strategy because the results are still not getting the desired results.

The analysis tools used in developing business processes at Burger Garage will include 2 parts, namely internal analysis, and external analysis. where each section will use a different approach. In the internal analysis, the future will use the analysis approach or method of resource. And finally external analysis, using 5 porters analysis and competitor analysis Furthermore, to analyze whether the social media promotions conducted by Burger Garage management are targeted effectively, a questionnaire will be distributed to determine whether social media promotions and influencers have an impact and influence customer purchase intentions. This is done to enable the management to understand the impact of each promotion on consumers. Afterwards, once all the data collection is completed, it will be combined based on qualitative analysis along with internal and external analysis using data directly obtained from Burger Garage customers to obtain accurate results.

3.4 Data Analysis Techniques

Descriptive statistical analysis, aims to analyze the data collected and used to identify the characteristics of each respondent and respondents' responses to the research variables, namely Social Media Promotion, Social Media Influencer, Customer Buying Interest. The answers to be analyzed can be seen from the number of scores obtained, as presented in the following table.

Table 3.1 Questionnaire Answer Score

Skor	Social Media Promotion	Social Media Influencer	Customer Buying Interest
1	Strongly Disagree	Strongly Disagree	Strongly Disagree
2	Disagree	Disagree	Disagree
3	Normal	Normal	Normal
4	Agree	Agree	Agree
5	Strongly Agree	Strongly Agree	Strongly Agree

Then the average score category for each variable is arranged to provide an overview of the user's assessment of each variable.

Table 3.2 Category Interval Value

Interval	Social Media Promotion	Social Media Influencer	Customer Buying Interest
1.00 - 1.80	Strongly Poor	Strongly Poor	Strongly Poor
1.81 - 2.60	Poor	Not Pleased	Not Good
2.61 - 3.40	Normal	Normal	Normal
3.41 - 4.20	Good	Pleased	Good
4.21 - 5.00	Strongly Good	Strongly Pleased	Strongly Good

After the data is collected, the next step is to process the data. Broadly speaking, the steps of data processing are::

1. To measure the opinion of respondents in this study, the scale used in the questionnaire is a Likert scale which is naturally an ordinal scale (Sekaran & Bougie, 2013) with 5 alternative answers.
2. Next, the total score of each variable is calculated = the sum of the scores of all indicator variables from all respondents
3. Calculating the score of each variable = the average of the total score
4. Determining the interval in 5 ranks, using the formula:

Information:

P = Interval class length

Interval = Maximum score – minimum score

A number of classes = 5

In the questionnaire in this study the maximum score for each questionnaire is 5 and the minimum score is 1 and the number of classes is 5.

Table 3.3 Questionnaire Answer Guidelines

Answer Options	Score (positive)	Score (negative)
Strongly Agree (SA)	5	1
Agree (A)	4	2
Normal (N)	3	3
Disagree (D)	2	4
Strongly Disagree (SD)	1	5

The score will be used to determine the value of biggest and smallest percentage by dividing the cumulative score (x) with the biggest cumulative score then multiplied by 100 percent.

$$\text{Biggest percentage} = 200 \times 5 = 1000 > \times 100\% = 100\%$$

$$\text{Smallest percentage} = 200 \times 1 = 200 > \times 100\% = 20\%$$

Then the score range categories for each variable are arranged in order to provide an overview of the respondent's assessment of each variable so that the range value is obtained through the result of subtraction between the largest and smallest percentages and then divided by the number of scales used.

$$\text{Range Value} = 100\% - 20\% = 80\% > = 16$$

Based on the calculation above, the continuum line will be presented as follows:

Figure 3.2 Interval Value Category

Source: Processed Data (2022)

The focus of this research is to use a variance-based Structural Equation Model (SEM) approach and is presented with partial least squares (PLS) analysis as one of the tools in the research. The advantages of SEM by using PLS are as follows:

1. This model is a model that was first built (theory development), previously there was no similar model (relationships between variables in research) so that there was no theoretical backing that could be referred to as a covariance-based model development,

2. As a newly developed research model, PLS accommodates indicators that are either reflective, formative, or both.

According to Vinzi, Chin, Henseler, Wang (2010) in the Handbook of Partial Least Squares: Concept, Method and Applications, that the reflective model, the block of manifest variables associated with latent variables is assumed to measure a unique basic concept. Each manifest variable reflects (is the effect of) the corresponding latent variable and plays the role of the endogenous variable in a particular block of measurement models. In a reflective measurement model, indicators related to the same latent variable must be covariant: a change in one indicator implies a change in the other.

If the research is exploratory (for example, in this research, which is the first time it has been conducted, instead of explaining the relationship between variables from previous studies, the construction of variables comes from formative indicators). In the formative model, each empirical indicator represents an indicator that is neither homogeneous nor unidimensional. All indicators form a combination of regression equations in explaining the latent construct. All indicators must have a common variance (covariance) so that eliminating one indicator does not change the role of other indicators. This research model is divided into two stages, namely Evaluation of Measurement (Outer Model) and Testing of Structural Models (Inner Model).

Evaluation of Measurement (Outer Model)

Validity Test and Reliability Test

Test the accuracy of a measuring instrument can be done by testing the validity. The validity of an instrument can be proven from content validity, construct validity, and criterion validity. The results of the instrument test and its criteria are then connected to the correlation test (Yusup, 2018). The following will present the correlation formula to obtain the correlation coefficient from the results of instrument testing.

Description:

r = correlation coefficient

n = total respondents

x = score of each instrument item

y = score for each criterion item

The accuracy of the criteria is assessed by comparing the instrument items with the criteria items. Comparisons were tested by correlation test. The more the value of the validity coefficient is close to +1.00, the more valid the instrument can be indicated. In PLS-SEM, the validity test consists of 2 types, namely the convergent and discriminant validity tests. The parameters considered in the convergent validity test are the loading factor with a validity coefficient of more than 0.7 and AVE (Average Variance Extracted) with a validity coefficient of more than 0.5 (Garson, 2016). The AVE value can be calculated by taking into account the loading factor value using the following formula:

For the discriminant validity test, the parameters to consider are the Fornell Larcker Criterion ($\sqrt{\text{AVE}} > \text{correlation of latent variables}$) and cross loading with a validity coefficient of more than 0.7 in one variable so that the instrument is declared valid (Garson, 2016). The AVE value can be calculated by taking the square root of the AVE value. Reliability test pays attention to the extent to which a measurement instrument can be trusted because of its stability. An instrument is said to be reliable if the composite reliability coefficient, ρ_A and Cronbach's Alfa reliability coefficient is more than 0.7 (Garson, 2016; Yusup, 2018). The Cronbach Alpha reliability coefficient formula is as follows:

Description:

r_i = AlfaCronbach reliability coefficient

k = number of question items

$\sum s_i^2$ = total variance score for each item

s^2 = varians total

The data analysis method used in this research is multivariate analysis. Multivariate analysis is the analysis of several variables in a relationship or a set of relationships (Hair et al, 2014). The multivariate analysis used in this study was using the Structural Equation Modeling with partial least squares (SEM-PLS) technique.

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Structural Model Testing (Inner Model)

In this study, the structural model testing (which aims to test the hypothesis in SEM) will use Partial Least Square (PLS) analysis which is a variance-based SEM method. On the next page, several reasons why the author applies PLS-SEM as a research tool (Krasnova et al., 2008).

1. Sample size. It is expected that the sample size (which is relatively small) does not affect the results of the developed model.
2. Normality of data. PLS does not require a large sample so that the normality of the data is also not a requirement for the formation of a structural model.
3. The nature of the indicator. As a newly developed model, PLS accommodates indicators that are either reflective, formative, or both.

According to Solihin and Ratmono (2013), there are 7 stages in the PLS-SEM analysis which will be presented on the next page. (Solihin & Ratmono, 2013)

PLS-SEM can work efficiently with relatively small sample sizes and complex models (Solihin & Ratmono, 2013). By using the SmartPLS version 3 software as a supporter of data analysis. The author will present on the next page an evaluation table of the goodness of fit criteria of PLS-SEM which is used to evaluate the results of the measurement and structural model testing.

Table 3.4 Evaluation of the Goodness of Fit Criteria

Outer Model Goodnes of Fit	
Validitas Konvergen	Syarat
Faktor/Outer Loading	More then 0,7
AVE	More then 0,5
Validitas Diskriminan	
Fornell Larcker Criterion	AVE. Latent Variable Correlation
Cross Loading	More then 0,7
Alfa Cronbach & rho A	More then 0,7
Inner Model Goodness of Fit Index	
R Square/ R ²	(Contribution/ coefficient of determination) (The higher and the closer to 1, the better)

Effect size/ f^2	(Magnitude of influence) (The higher and the closer to 1, the better)
Uji Hipotesis (Bootstrapping)	
T-Values	>1,974
P-Values	<0,05

Hypothesis Testing Design

The hypothesis is used to see whether there is an influence between latent variables. The hypothesis is carried out by determining the null hypothesis and alternative hypothesis, statistical test research and calculating the value of statistical and hypothesis tests, determining the level of significance and drawing conclusions. Statistical test (t-test) is to determine how far the influence of an individual exogenous variable is in explaining the variation of endogenous variables. The hypothesis is accepted significantly if the value is <0.05. Statistical test (t-test) was used on hypothesis 1 to hypothesis 3.

The criteria used in the t-test are:

1. Ho: $\gamma_1 = 0$; It means that there is no partially significant effect on each variable.
2. H1: $\gamma_1 \neq 0$; It means that there is a partially significant effect on each variable.

While the test criteria are:

1. Significant level $\alpha = 0,05$.
2. Distribution of t with degrees of freedom (n).
3. If t count > t table then Ho is rejected and H1 is accepted and vice versa.

4. FINDING: BUSINESS SOLUTION

4.1 Analysis of Business Situation

This section discusses the profile of the respondents. The figure of the profile shows the data from general to quite specific. It is expected could help Burger Garage to generate the strategy to increase consumers buying interest.

4.1.1 Survey Results

The characteristics of the respondents are shown in the following figure which includes characteristics based on gender, age, occupation and monthly incomes of the consumers of Burger Garage

4.1.2 Characteristics of Respondent

A. Gender of Respondent

Based on the gender composition of the respondents, it can be seen in the figure below:

Figure 4.1 Gender Characteristics
Source: Processed Data (2023)

Based on the data on gender characteristics in, it is known that there were more female respondents (59%) than female respondents (41%). This reveals that consumers at burger garage are relatively balanced, because the management at burger garage is very friendly and the food served is friendly and loved by both of them.

B. Age of Respondent

Figure 4.2 Age of Respondent Characteristics
Source: Processed Data (2023)

Based on the data above, from the age group of 18 to 25 years with a value of 53 percent, then the age group 26 -34 years old with a score of 39 percent. Followed by the age group under 17 years with 7 percent, and the last age group of 35 years and over with 1 percent. it can be concluded that consumers at burger garage have a balanced percentage based on the age group of millennial consumers. This happens because the service from burger garage does not look at age, everything is served properly according to company standards.

C. Occupation of Respondent

Figure 4.3 Occupation Characteristics
Source: Processed Data (2023)

Based on the Occupations data in Figure, it is known that the respondent’s occupation was dominated by employees with 39 percent, followed by the occupation of student with 36 percent, and Entrepreneur/Self-employed with 13 percent and the last Civil Servant with 12 percent.

D. Monthly Incomes of Respondent

Figure 4.4 Monthly Income Characteristics
 Source: Processed Data (2023)

Based on the monthly income data in Figure, it is known that the respondent’s monthly income was dominated by consumer with monthly income below 4,500,000 IDR with value 51 percent, then followed by respondents with monthly income in the range of 4,500,001 - 6,000,000 IDR with a value of 30 percent, then followed by respondents with monthly income in the range of 6,000,001 - 10,000,000 IDR. respondents with monthly income in the range of 10,000,001 - 15,000,000 IDR have a value of 4 percent. and the last respondent with a monthly income of more than 15,000,000 IDR as much as 1 percent. This explains that the prices offered for products at Burger Garage are very friendly and affordable for all groups of people

4.1.3 Result Data Analysis

The following are descriptive results of the variables used in the study, namely social media promotions, social media influencers, customer buying interest, and brand trust. These results are followed by grouping the results into predefined categories.

A. Social Media Promotion

Table 4.1 Results of Descriptive Analysis of Social Media Promotion Variables

Social Media Promotion (X1)	Indicator	SD	D	N	A	SA	Total Resp	Total Score	%	Mean
		1	2	3	4	5				
Content Creator	X1.1	0	0	38	147	15	200	777	77.70	77.70
Content Sharing	X1.2	0	0	44	139	17	200	773	77.30	77.30

Connecting	X1.3	0	0	44	132	24	200	780	78.00	78.00
Community Building	X1.4	0	0	51	135	14	200	763	76.30	76.65
	X1.5	0	0	48	134	18	200	770	77.00	
TOTAL MEAN									77.41	

Based on table 4.1, it is known that the average score for the social media promotion variable is included in the high category (68.1 percent x 84 percent) which is 77.41 percent, That is, the average respondent considers that the variable social media promotion is in a high category where social media promotion is considered important for consumers, because with this consumers can find out the latest offers from burger garage.

B. Social Media Influencer

Table 4.2 Results of Descriptive Analysis of Social Media Influencer Variables

Social Media Influencer(X2)	Indicator	SD	D	N	A	SA	Total Resp	Total Score	%	Mean
		1	2	3	4	5				
Good Credibility	X2.1	0	0	33	153	14	200	781	78.10	78.35
	X2.2	0	0	30	154	16	200	786	78.60	
High Activity	X2.3	0	0	32	152	16	200	784	78.40	78.35
	X2.4	0	0	37	143	20	200	783	78.30	
Large Following	X2.5	0	0	44	139	17	200	773	77.30	77.30
TOTAL MEAN									78.00	

Based on table 4.2, it is known that the average score for the social media influencer variable is included in the high category (68.1 percent x 84 percent) which is 78.00 percent, That is, the average respondent considers that the social media influencer variable is in a high category where social media influencers are considered important for consumers, because with this consumers can follow their idols and want what their idols do.

C. Customer Buying Interest

Table 4.3 Results of Descriptive Analysis of Customer Buying Interest Variables

Customers Buying Interest (Y)	Indicator	SD	D	N	A	SA	Total Resp	Total Score	%	Mean
		1	2	3	4	5				
Attention	Y.1	0	0	38	147	15	200	777	77.70	77.70
Interest	Y.2	0	0	44	136	20	200	776	77.60	77.60
Desire	Y.3	0	0	39	142	19	200	780	78.00	78.00
Action	Y.4	0	0	56	126	18	200	762	76.20	75.85
	Y.5	0	0	60	125	15	200	755	75.50	
TOTAL MEAN										77.29

Based on table 4.3, it is known that the average score for the consumer buying interest variable is included in the high category (68.1 percent x 84 percent) which is 77.29 percent, That is, the average respondent considers that the customer buying interest variable is in a high category where customer buying interest are considered important for management burger garage, because with this Management can find out what things can make consumers want to buy Burger Garage products and what consumers want.

D. Brand Trust

Table 4.4 Results of Descriptive Analysis of Brand Trust Variables

Brand Trust (Z)	Indicator	SD	D	N	A	SA	Total Resp	Total Score	%	Mean
		1	2	3	4	5				
Reliability	Z.1	0	0	27	140	33	200	794	79.40	79.40
Integrity'	Z.2	0	0	36	134	30	200	806	80.60	80.60
TOTAL MEAN										80.00

Based on table 4.4, it is known that the average score for the brand trust variable is included in the high category (68.1 percent x 84 percent) which is 80.00 percent. That is, the average respondent considers that the customer buying interest variable is in a high category where customer buying interest is considered important for management of a burger garage. Because from the results of the questionnaire, consumers are more trusting and want to buy a product if the company or brand name has a good image.

4.1.4 Validity and Reliability Test Result

The purpose of this study's data analysis using SmartPLS is to determine the reliability and validity of the questionnaire design, measurement scale, concept selection, and indicator translation into measurement items. The validity of a model may be assessed by assessing its construct and indicator (reliability), as well as its convergent and discriminant (validity); the findings are summarized in the tables below. Cronbach alpha and composite reliability (CR) are used to construct reliability, with 0.7 serving as the lower cutoff. The lowest allowable level of outer loading for indication reliability is 0.7. However, if the CR and average variance extracted (AVE) values are already over the threshold, outer loadings between 0.4 and 0.7 may be preserved. Additionally, convergent validity is determined by the AVE values of each construct, which must be greater than 0.5.

Table 4.5 Outer Loadings

	<i>Loadings factor dan Cross Loading</i>					
	Z	Y	X2	X1	Average Variance Extracted (AVE)	Explanation
X1.1	0.755	0.726	0.59	0.716	0.648	Valid
X1.2	0.389	0.759	0.755	0.871		Valid
X1.3	0.427	0.808	0.808	0.909		Valid
X1.4	0.481	0.662	0.663	0.703		Valid
X2.1	0.647	0.734	0.881	0.683	0.647	Valid
X2.2	0.53	0.642	0.765	0.535		Valid
X2.3	0.389	0.75	0.762	0.877		Valid
Y1	0.755	0.726	0.59	0.716	0.547	Valid
Y2	0.403	0.784	0.772	0.827		Valid
Y3	0.45	0.727	0.604	0.56		Valid
Y4	0.373	0.72	0.637	0.576		Valid
Z1	0.780	0.48	0.534	0.459	0.690	Valid
Z2	0.878	0.626	0.547	0.582		Valid

Based on the table, the measurement results have met the convergent validity requirements where the social media promotion variable consisting of 4 dimensions with each loading factor value is greater than 0.7. The biggest influence for the online marketing variable (X1) in this study is connecting dimension with an effect of 0.909. Then for the offline marketing variable (X2), the dimension with the greatest influence is represented by the good credibility dimension with a value of 0.881. Then for the brand trust variable (Z), the dimension with the greatest influence is represented by the integrity dimension with a value of 0.878. the last for the variable customer buying interest (Y), the biggest influence is represented by the Interest dimension with a value of 0.784.

Table 4.6 Construct Reliability and Validity

	Cronbach's Alpha	rho_A	Composite Reliability	Explanation
Brand Trust (Z)	0.756	0.782	0.816	Reliable
Customer Buying Interest (Y)	0.726	0.735	0.828	Reliable
Social Media Influencer (X2)	0.725	0.729	0.846	Reliable
Social Media Promotion(X1)	0.813	0.823	0.879	Reliable
X1 Against Y with Z as moderator	1.000	1.000	1.000	Reliable
X2 Against Y with Z as moderator	1.000	1.000	1.000	Reliable

Based on the data above, it can be observed that all of the requirements for construct reliability, indicator reliability, and convergent validity were met in this test. Despite the fact that certain loading levels are more than 0.7. There are two loading values around 0.5 and six around 0.6, but Cronbach alpha and construct reliability values more than 0.7, with one Cronbach alpha around the 0.6 limits. Furthermore, one of the AVE values is close to 0.5 and the others are greater than 0.5, indicating that the indicators and construct used in this research are likely to provide a consistent result.

The discriminant validity may also be determined by looking at the cross loading of the items. When an indicator's loading on its assigned concept is greater than all of its cross-loadings with other constructs, discriminant validity is attained (Hair et al., 2017). Because all of the cross-loading values of the items in the assigned construct are greater than the other cross-loading values, the result shows that all items have discriminant validity.

R-Squared (R2 or coefficient of determination) is a statistical parameter in a regression model that indicates how much variation in the dependent variable can be explained by the independent variable. In other words, r-squared indicates the degree to which the data conform to the regression model (the goodness of fit). R- squared values less than 0.5 are often used to forecast human behavior, since humans are naturally difficult to anticipate. The R squared value of the data in this research is more than 50%, or 0.5, indicating that the data fit the regression model effectively.

Table 4.7 R-Square

	R Square	R Square Adjusted
Y	0.884	0.881

Based on table 4.7, it is known that the r square value was 0.884, and this value was in the moderate category. It shows that the Online marketing and Offline Marketing can explain Consumer Buying Interest by 88.4 percent. At the same time, the remaining 11.6 percent was explained by other variables not included in the study.

The figure below shows the results of model testing as follows;

Figure 4.5 Loading Factor (PLS Algorithm)

Source: Processed Data, 2023

Figure 4.5 shows the values for the loading factor in the analysis of the measurement model (outer model) and the coefficients of influence for the structural model (inner model).

The research hypothesis test was carried out by looking at the parameter coefficient values and the significance value of the T-statistic and the P-values <5% T-statistic (T-count) was used to determine the quality of the significance between each independent variable (X), whether it had an influence or not on the dependent variable (Y), the following is a recapitulation of the results of data processing which is shown in table below:

Table 4.8 Path Coefficients (Bootstrapping)

	Original Sample (O)	Sample Mean (M)	T Statistics (O/STDEV)	P Values
Brand Trust (Z) -> Customer Buying Interest (Y)	0.124	0.127	3.867	0.000
Social Media Influencer (X2) -> Customer Buying Interest (Y)	0.287	0.280	4.557	0.000
Social Media Promotion(X1) -> Customer Buying Interest (Y)	0.595	0.599	9.635	0.000
X1 Against Y with Z as Moderator -> Customer Buying Interest	-0.070	-0.069	1.972	0.048
X2 Against Y with Z as moderator -> Customer Buying Interest	0.106	0.106	1.973	0.028

Hypothesis 1 Result

Hypothesis 1 (H1) in this study suggests that there is a positive and significant influence between social media promotion variables and consumer buying interest variables, this is based on the value of t statistic > t table that was 9.635 > 1.971. The significance level is represented by p-values of 0.000 < 0.05, which fulfilled the p-values < significance level and path coefficient value of 0.595. It shows that social media promotion (X1) had a positive and significant effect on consumer buying interest (Y). Which means that social media promotion is directly proportional to consumer buying interest, where the higher the social media promotion activities carried out, the higher the consumer buying interest.

This is supported by previous research case studies on customers Bukalapak researched by Ladya R, (2016) case study on Fani House Online Shop Bag Consumers, from the research conducted that showed is a significant influence between social media promotion and consumer buying interest. This means that the better and more attractive social media promotion carried out will be able to attract consumer buying interest.

Hypothesis 2 Result

Hypothesis 2 (H2) This study shows that there is a negative and significant influence between social media influencer variables on consumer buying interest variables with brand trust as a moderator variable, this is based on the value of t statistic $>$ t table that was $4.557 > 1.971$. The significance level is represented by p-values of $0.000 < 0.05$, which fulfilled the p-values $<$ significance level and path coefficient value of 0.287. It shows that social media influencer (X2) had a positive and significant effect on consumer buying interest (Y). Which means that social media influencer is directly proportional to consumer buying interest, where the higher the social media influencer engagement carried out, the higher the consumer buying interest

This is supported by previous research which suggests that one of the main ones that can influence consumer buying interest on social networking sites is electronic word-of-mouth (Zhu et al., 2016). Other influential factors are:the credibility of social media influencers in endorsement situations (Hui, 2017; Sokolova and Kefi, 2019).

Hypothesis 3 Result

Hypothesis 3 (H3) in this study suggests that there is a negative and significant influence between social media promotion variables and consumer buying interest variables, this is based on the value of t statistic $>$ t table that was $1.972 > 1.971$. The significance level is represented by p-values of $0.048 < 0.05$, which fulfilled the p-values $<$ significance level and path coefficient value of -0.070. This shows that social media promotion (X1) with brand trust as a moderator variable (Z) has a negative and significant effect on consumer buying interest (Y). This is because there is a contrast between the social media promotion of a product when compared to brand trust, consumers look more at whether the brand can be trusted or not, so that social media promotion with brand trust as a moderator variable is inversely proportional to consumer buying interest, meaning that the higher the social media activity carried out if the brand cannot be trusted, it will not be left behind by consumers.

Hypothesis 4 Result

Hypothesis 4 (H4) in this study suggests that there is a positive and significant influence between social media influencer variables and consumer buying interest variables, this is based on the value of t statistic $>$ t table that was $1.973 > 1.971$. The significance level is represented by p-values of $0.028 < 0.05$, which fulfilled the p-values $<$ significance level and path coefficient value of 0.106. This shows that social media influencer (X2) with brand trust as a moderator variable (Z) has a positive and significant effect on consumer buying interest (Y). Which means that social media influencers with brand trust as a moderator variable are directly proportional to consumer buying interest, where the better social media influencers and brand trust will directly increase consumer buying interest

4.2 Internal Analysis

In this section, the researcher will analyze the internal factor use of resources and capabilities of Burger Garage.

4.2.1 Resources

The inputs that a firm/company uses to create products or services is called resources. In many cases, some resources are rather undifferentiated inputs that any firm or company can acquire. Both tangible and intangible capabilities refer to a firm/company's skill in using its resources. The characteristic of tangible resources can be described as assets that can be observed and quantified. On the other hand, intangible resources are assets that are rooted deeply in the company's history and accumulated over time (Kotler & Armstrong, 2018)

At first burger garage started from Chef name Arsyian Dwianto, he is best known for joining cooking competition call MasterCheff Indonesia. Now he is the owner of Burger Garage he started this business in 2020 from personal order every week to friends, and family. In late 2020 he started to create restaurant in Cipete South Jakarta in the back of his father's business car garage. The reason for the restaurant is in Cipete because is near many of restaurant therefore many of people eat in this area so it easy for Burger Garage to be more recognized at first.

4.2.2 Competitor Analysis

Competition is one of the most critical aspects of today's business world. No matter what firm is, big or small, or what area of business sector your business is in, it always has a competitor in the industry, and all competitors can affect the process of formulating a strategic plan. Analyzing an organization's competitors helps to discover weaknesses and identify opportunities and threats from the industrial environment (Adom, 2016).

Most companies use competition analysis to please current and potential customers. Internet and websites are used where companies place information concerning items like prices of their products, suppliers, and marketing promos. This will give an insight into where the company is heading and differentiation from the competitors (Kelvin, M, 2008).

Most competitor analyses help new businesses understand the market; by having a competitor, most businesses have a clear idea of what product can ensure success.

The author shows some of Burger Garage's competitors through social media images and distinct characters and communication styles adopted in their social media.

1. Lawless Burger

The name Lawless Burger is inspired by heavy metal and pop rock names. The burger joint is located in the South Kemang area. They used a heavy metal and pop-rock atmosphere in their restaurant, and the menu also named from heavy metal and pop-rock bands, musicians, or even song titles.

Figure 4.8 Lawless Burger Logo

Figure 4.9 Lawless Burger Social Media

2. Ask For Patty

The second competitor is Ask For Patty. The restaurant mostly focuses on its casual dining venue with a fun and vibrant vibe that track customers to visit their diners and pay for their delicious burger. Ask For Patty is known for its all-American style burger because its patty uses the best quality beef with a meticulous method that results in a juicy and meaty flavor.

Figure 4.10 Ask For Patty Restaurant

Figure 4.11 Ask For Patty Social Media

3. Five Monkeys

Five Monkeys is a burger joint that serves simple, fresh California-style burgers. Five Monkeys has the prestige to become the best 27 burger in the world from Bloomberg pursuit in 2017.

Figure 4.12 Five Monkeys

Figure 4.13 Five Monkeys Social Media

Table 4.9 Competitor Analysis

Brand	Product	Price	Place	Promotion
Lawless Burger	Juicy burgers with tasty taste, the size of burgers is big therefore it help with customers liking. Have uniqueness with the name of burger based on Metal/ Rocks performers, songs.	Rp. 100.000 - Rp. 200.000	Online delivery: Shopee food, GoFood, Grab Food. Offline Store most notable places with a high crowded area, such as Kemang, Bintaro, or Menteng	Marketing Strategy: Social Media Promotion, Online Promotion, Social Media Influencer
Ask For Patty	Juicy Burgers using brisket for the burgers to be more tasty. The price is affordable compare with the three burgers. Use Brisket beef with the Burgers make them more delicious.	Rp. 50.000 - Rp. 100.000	Online delivery: Shopee food, GoFood, Grab Food. Offline Store most notable places with a high crowded area, such as Menteng, Grand Indonesia.	Marketing Strategy: Social Media Promotion, Online Promotion, Social Media Influencer
Five Monkeys	Five Monkeys is one of Burger joint not only focusing on their burgers but they have Hot Dog, and corn Dog in the restaurant. Focusing on their Family theme Five Monkeys are notably the top 27 Burgers in the world by Bloomberg.	Rp. 50.000 - Rp. 100.000	Online delivery: Shopee food, GoFood, Grab Food. Offline Store focusing on malls like Sarinah and croded area in Panglima Polim	Marketing Strategy: Social Media Promotion, Online Promotion, Social Media Influencer

Source: Author 2023

4.3 External Analysis

In this section, the author will analyze the external factor that is used by industry analysis which include Porter’s Five Forces, Competitor Analysis Burger Garage.

4.3.1 The Porter's 5 Forces Analysis

A case in this study is the Food and beverage Industry (Burger) with analysis based on Porter's Five Force. Porter's Five Force model is used to analyze economic factors that affect the level of competition in the market. The model uses economic tools to analyze the Food and beverage (Burger) Industry with a based analysis to establish how companies in the industry react to threats, and opportunities to ensure they turn a profit. Porter's Five-Force model acts as a strategic platform for generating strategic choices (Hill and Jones, 2014)

Figure 4.14 Porter Five Force Model

Source: (Hill and Jones, 2014)

1. **Industry competition (High):** A higher degree of competition means the power of competing companies decreases. When competition is low, companies can do whatever they need to in order to increase their profits. The competition in the food and beverage industry in Jakarta is to more in the medium spectrum. Burger garage has only one outlet, and now are planning to expand and build a new restaurant at Menteng , and BSD because in the two areas the company has a direct competitor therefore Burger Garage can just enter the market.
2. **New players in the industry (High):** New (and more) entrants into the market mean a company's power also decreases. Most companies prefer to operate in a market or industry where there are fewer players.
3. **Supplier (seller) power (Medium):** This factor examines how suppliers can use their power to increase the price of goods and services. The fewer suppliers there are in the market means they have more power.
4. **Buyer (customer) power (High):** When consumers have more bargaining power, they may be able to affect the price of goods and services, driving them down. Winning the customers is a must because the market has many alternative companies to turn to. Maintaining a good customer relationship becomes one of the strategies to increase customer loyalty despite the number of existing competitors. The characteristics of start-up consumer profiles and small to medium-sized business were to build their own Teste that could accommodate their business.
5. **The threat of substitutes (High):** Products and services by a rival that can easily be substituted are also a threat to a business's profitability.

4.3.2 Interpretation Industry Analysis

Based on the collected data above regarding competitive rivalry, the threat of new entrants and substitutes of products could also have bargaining power for suppliers and customers. This table below concludes of industry analysis:

Table 4.11 Interpretation Industry Analysis

Forces	Analysis	Interpretation
Rivalry among competitors	High	Unattractive Industry (Low profit tendencies)
Bargaining power of buyers	High	
Bargaining power of suppliers	High	
Threat of substitute products	Medium	
Threat of new entrants	High	

According to the table above, it could be concluded that the industry is unattractive, therefore the company could risk entering a low profit business. The characteristic of the industry makes it difficult for the company to achieve strategic competitiveness and earn above-average returns

4.3.3 4P Marketing Mix

From the interview with the owner of Burger Garage, it has been summarized as an implementation of 4P Marketing to ensure the improvement of Burger Garage.

1. Product

- Produce new set menus that can track new customers using Indonesian tastes as the primary resource.
- Create a new target market by targeting customers that love Motor GP or other sports rather than Formula One.
- Increase the new variety of burgers.
- Collaborating with famous chefs such as Chef Renanta and Willgoz to create new products.
- Discover new market trends and customer preferences.

2. Price

- Create menus that below Rp. 50.000 to help customers who want to try Burger Garages.
- Joining Gofood, Shopee Food, Grab food Promos.
- It has two price categories that can cover the two classes: middle class and upper middle class.

3. Place

- Burger Garage has a strategic location; therefore, they need to have events to attract more customers.
- Burger Garage is next to a car garage; therefore, find an Auto club to have them check their vehicle and enjoy Burger garage foods.
- Decided new branches based on competitors' locations so burger garages can enter the market easily.

4. Promotion

- Finding a new Social Media specialist that can help Burger Garage Social Media have the same content rather than changing it with different ideas.
- Find new partnerships that have prominent individuals in the Food and Beverage industry, including Influencers and burger enthusiasts.
- Becoming a food, and beverage partner with a motorsports club can help them track new customers.
- Promote the dining experience on social media.
- Collaborate with Food and Beverage events that can help promote the businesses.

4.4 Solution and Proposed Implementation Plan

Burger Garage can execute this marketing promotion strategy, build brand awareness, and boost sales by doing the strategies that have been created for the next three months. The strategies can be implemented by having the company monitor and understand the goals that have been needed for the businesses to be more successful. The strategy focuses on improving marketing strategy by having social media influencer, promos, and gaining new marketing target.

Table 4.12 Implementation Plan Timeline

Strategies	Objective	2023												
		September				October				November				
		Week				Week				Week				
		I	II	III	IV	I	II	III	IV	I	II	III	IV	
Product	Produce new set menus that can track new customers using Indonesian tastes as the primary resource.	■	■	■										
	Create a new target market by targeting customers that love Motor GP or other sports rather than Formula One.				■	■								
	Increase the new variety of burgers.						■	■						
	Collaborating with famous chefs such as Chef Renanta and Willgoz to create new products.									■	■			
	Discover new market trends and customer preferences.	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	
Price	Joining Gofood, Shopee Food, Grab food Promos.	■	■	■	■	■								
	Create menus that below Rp. 50.000 to help customers who want to try Burger Garages.						■	■	■	■				
	It has two price categories that can cover the two classes: middle class and upper middle class.										■	■	■	
Places	Burger Garage has a strategic location; therefore, they need to have events to attract more customers.	■	■	■	■									
	Burger Garage is next to a car garage; therefore, find an Auto club to have them check their vehicle and enjoy Burger garage foods.	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	
	Decided new branches based on competitors' locations so burger garages can enter the market easily.									■	■	■	■	
Promotion	Finding a new Social Media specialist that can help Burger Garage Social Media have the same content rather than changing it with different ideas.	■	■	■										
	Find new partnerships that have prominent individuals in the Food and Beverage industry, including Influencers and burger enthusiasts.				■	■	■	■						
	Becoming a food, and beverage partner with a motorsports club can help them track new customers.	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	
	Promote the dining experience on social media.									■	■			
	Collaborate with Food and Beverage events that can help promote the businesses.										■	■	■	

The table above shows the implementation strategy that Burger Garage will execute. This will be ensured by regular monitoring of market trends, competitor activity, and customer feedback. The strategy focuses on Burger Garage's social media, which can be utilized by having new events, promos, and more influencers to review the food. This will make it more appealing to the audience and boost revenue for the business.

4.4.1 Justification Implementation Plan

The implementation plan for Burger Garage has been discussed with the owner and the teams; this plan ensures the business succeeds by using social media to effectively target primary objectives, seek new market opportunities, and increase brand expansion.

The plan has identified key strategies, including product development, pricing strategies, social media targeting, and new ventures. Having learned from customers, the evidence shows the strategies that have been implemented can successfully succeed in their customer expectations, making them more aware of the products.

Based on the feedback from the owner, there are some plans that they already did but did not succeed, but by creating this implemented plan, Burger Garage will take the approach by sorting the same aspects that can match the business strategy.

5. CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATION

5.1 Conclusion

In light of the overall findings of this final research project, five conclusions derived that could be used to address three research questions and objectives as stated below:

1. Social media promotion (X1) had a positive and significant effect on consumer buying interest (Y). Which means that social media promotion is directly proportional to consumer buying interest, where the higher the social media promotion activities carried out, the higher the consumer buying interest.
2. Social media influencer (X2) had a positive and significant effect on consumer buying interest (Y). Which means that social media influencer is directly proportional to consumer buying interest, where the higher the social media influencer engagement carried out, the higher the consumer buying interest
3. Social media promotion (X1) with brand trust as a moderator variable (Z) has a negative and significant effect on consumer buying interest (Y). This is because there is a contrast between the social media promotion of a product when compared to brand trust, consumers look more at whether the brand can be trusted or not, so that social media promotion with brand trust as a moderator variable is inversely proportional to consumer buying interest, meaning that the higher the social media activity carried out if the brand cannot be trusted, it will not be left behind by consumers.
4. Social media influencer (X2) with brand trust as a moderator variable (Z) has a positive and significant effect on consumer buying interest (Y). Which means that social media influencers with brand trust as a moderator variable are directly proportional to consumer buying interest, where the better social media influencers and brand trust will directly increase consumer buying interest
5. As a result of this research analysis, burger garage can implement several strategy recommendations both from the internal and external management sides. This recommendations plan ensures the business succeeds by using social media to effectively target primary objectives, seek new market opportunities, and increase brand expansion. The recommendations plan has identified key strategies, including product development, pricing strategies, social media targeting, and new ventures. Having learned from customers, the evidence shows the strategies that have been implemented can successfully succeed in their customer expectations, making them more aware of the products.

5.2 Recommendation

Referring to the conclusions of the research results, there are several suggestions that need to be expressed in this study:

1. This research reveals that social media promotion, social media influencers and brand trust are closely related to consumer buying interest in burger garage companies, so management must always maximize social media and uphold the integrity of the company as a means of promotion and influence to run its business so as not to be left behind by competitors
2. Implement continuous management in its business lines so that management can find out mistakes and waste that occur in burger garage, and do not forget to create a means of customer feedback so that they can find out customer expectations of burger garage.

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